

Element	Air temperature	Relative humidity	Temperature		Radiation		Heat flux			
			Water	Soil	Total	Net	Soil	Latent	Sensible	
Canopy	Emission (E)	-0.05	-0.23	0.57**	0.67**	-0.08	-0.04	-0.39	0.70**	0.36
	E/LAI	-0.18	0.06	0.51*	0.60**	0.01	0.47	-0.77**	0.57*	0.56**
Water surface	Emission (E)	0.53*	-0.44	0.85**	0.77**	0.38	0.36	-0.74**	0.79**	0.81**
	E/LAI	0.20	-0.07	0.62**	0.63**	0.26	0.28	-0.87**	0.59**	0.74**

the highest correlation with soil heat flux ($r = 0.77^{**}$) compared with the other elements. This finding suggests that solar energy plays an important role as a thermal energy source for CH₄ emission, and that the amount of energy reaching the ground where methanogenic bacteria live may be more important than previously thought in determining CH₄ emission. (See the figure for temporal changes in daily means of water and ground temperatures along with CH₄ emission rates estimated as a function of these temperatures.)

We determined the estimation models by combining the respective estimation formulas developed under either bright or dark conditions. CH₄ emission were estimated by using one of two regression equations: $Y = -2347.12 + 221.5488x - 3.75347x^2$ as a function of water temperature or $Y = -3205.08 + 27.501x - 1.29756x^2$ as a function of ground temperature. During the early growing

Seasonal changes in water temperature, ground temperature, and CH₄ emission estimated as a function of these two temperatures. Suwon, Korea, 1993.

season (from May to early June), CH₄ emission fluctuated greatly, depending strongly on the temporal variations in water and ground temperatures.

REFERENCES CITED

Conrad R (1989) Exchange of trace gases between terrestrial ecosystems and the atmosphere. Pages 39-58 in M. O. Adreae, and D. S. Sehmel eds. Wiley, Chichester.
 Schütz H, Seiler W, Conrad R (1989) Processes involved in formation and emission of methane in rice paddies. Biogeochemistry 7(1):33-53. ■

Impact of gypsum application on methane emission from a wetland ricefield

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A frequently suggested option to mitigate CH₄ emission from ricefields is use of sulfate-containing fertilizers, such as (NH₄)₂SO₄, because sulfate reducers (in the presence of SO₄²⁻) can outcompete methanogens for substrates (Martens and Berner 1974, Lovley and Klug 1983). Methanogens may coexist with sulfate reducers, however, when there are zones or spots with low sulfate content (Martens and Berner 1974). CH₄ emission measurements in ricefields fertilized with (NH₄)₂SO₄ gave contradicting results, presumably because of variations in *in situ* SO₄²⁻ concentrations in the different field experiments.

To elucidate the impact of sulfate availability on CH₄ emission, field experiments with gypsum (CaSO₄) application were carried out during the 1991 and 1992 wet seasons (WS) (Jul-Nov) in a wetland ricefield at Los Baños, Philippines. CH₄ emission rates were monitored with an automatic measurement system based on the closed chamber technique described by Schütz et al (1989), with minor modifications. CH₄ emission rates were calculated with linear regression from the temporal increase of the CH₄ concentration in the chamber ($Y^2 > 0.95$). The SO₄²⁻ concentration in the soil solution was measured on a dionex ionchromatograph at the beginning and end of the 1991 growing season.

CH₄ emission from fields with green manure (GM) was strongly enhanced

Average daily CH₄ flux from wetland ricefields in the Philippines with and without gypsum application. 1991-92.

Year	Fertilizer	Av CH ₄ flux (mg/m ² per d)	
		Without gypsum	With gypsum ^a
1991	Urea (55.2 kg N/ha)	40.2	18.6
1992	GM ^b + urea (30 kg N/ha)	443 ^c	128

^a6.66 t/ha CaSO₄ · 2H₂O. ^bGM = 20 t/ha (*Sesbania rostrata*). ^cAv flux calculated without extreme CH₄ emission rates (Fig. 1a).

compared with urea-fertilized plots (see table). The difference between CH₄ emission in the 1991 and 1992 WS cannot be attributed solely to GM application, because plant spacing, N fertilizer rate, and year were also different. The CH₄ emission from gypsum-amended plots was reduced by 55-70% compared with nonamended plots (see table).

In the first week after transplanting, the CH₄ emission from the GM-treated plot reached a peak value of 4.5 g/m² per d (Fig. 1a), probably caused by the quick turnover of easily decomposable organic C from the GM incorporated 1 wk before transplanting. No peak CH₄ emission was observed in the gypsum-amended plot. After the first week, the emission from both plots followed the same pattern, but emission levels differed significantly (Fig. 1b). The relative reduction in CH₄ emission upon gypsum application was independent of GM addition.

Competition for substrate between sulfate reducers and methanogens explains the lower CH₄ emission as a result of applying gypsum. In gypsum-treated soils, sulfur oxidation and a number of anaerobic thiobacilli were

found to be significantly higher than in control soils (Frenay et al 1982). Dissolved SO₄²⁻ in the control plot was below concentrations where sulfate reducers can outcompete methanogens, but after gypsum was applied, dissolved SO₄²⁻ was well above concentrations necessary for such competition. Initially high SO₄²⁻ concentrations will decrease with time through percolation of dissolved SO₄²⁻ and reduction by sulfate reducers. Cycling of S through oxidized zones, however, could maintain the inhibition of CH₄ production over a long time. CH₄ emission levels from the gypsum-amended plots never reached the level of the plots without gypsum addition (Fig. 1), indicating that methanogenesis was being inhibited throughout the season.

Despite clear evidence of sulfate-inhibiting methanogenesis, appreciable CH₄ emission still occurred in the gypsum-amended plots. The existence of zones or spots with low sulfate content where methanogenesis occurs implies that removal of sulfate by SO₄²⁻ reducers is quicker than its supply by dissolution of gypsum (or that the solid gypsum source was quickly depleted), and that cycling of S occurred in special zones (the oxidized rhizosphere) and the regenerated SO₄²⁻ is consumed before it is evenly distributed in the bulk soil.

The amount of gypsum in our study was within the normal range of gypsum amendments used to reclaim alkaline or sodic soils (Abrol et al 1985). In India alone, for example, several million ha of the Indo-Gangetic plain are alkaline soils on which rice is the major WS crop (Abrol et al 1985). The data from our study provide a base for reducing the estimates of CH₄ emission from rice grown on high sulfate-containing soils or gypsum-amended soils (by deriving a correction factor from Table 1). A small but significant part of the total area where rice is grown consists of soils that may be low producers of CH₄ because of competition between sulfate reducers and methanogens. In global budgets for CH₄ emission from rice production, these soils should be treated accordingly. Further research on other soil types covering a significant part of the world's rice area is needed to improve estimates of the contribution of rice cultivation to global CH₄ production.

REFERENCES CITED

- Abrol I P, Bhumbla D R, Meelu O P (1985) Influence of salinity and alkalinity on properties and management of ricelands. Pages 183-198 in Soil physics and rice. International Rice Research Institute, P. O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines.
- Frenay J R, Jacq V A, Baldensperger J F (1982) The significance of the biological sulfur cycle in rice production. Pages 271-313 in Microbiology of tropical soils and plant productivity. Y. R. Dommergues and H. G. Diem, eds. Nijhoff/Junk, Boston, USA.
- Lovley D R, Klug M J (1983) Appl. Environ. Microbiol. 45:187-192.
- Martens C S, Berner R A (1974) Science 185:1167-1169.
- Shütz H, Holzapfel-Pschorn A, Conrad R, Rennenberg H, Seiler W (1989) J. Geophys. Res. 94:16045-16416. ■